

Transformational Leadership and Project Performance: The Role of Employee Empowerment in Contractor-Subcontractor Dynamics in the Telecommunication Industry

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Abstract— Transformational leadership has been widely recognized for its positive impact on follower performance, particularly within project management frameworks. However, the underlying mechanisms that contribute to this performance enhancement remain unclear. This study aims to explore the influence of transformational leadership on project performance, with a specific focus on the role of employee empowerment. A questionnaire-based survey was conducted, collecting responses from 310 employees using a stratified sampling technique based on organizational roles. The findings reveal a significant positive relationship between transformational leadership and project performance, though there were notable gaps in the effective implementation of leadership styles. Furthermore, employee empowerment was found to have a substantial direct impact on performance, surpassing the influence of leadership effectiveness. The study also examined the moderating role of employee empowerment, which was found to have an insignificant effect. The results offer valuable recommendations for improving leadership execution and enhancing employee empowerment, along with suggestions for future Research in this area.

Keywords— Transformational Leadership, Project Performance, Employee empowerment, Project Management

I. INTRODUCTION

Effective leadership and employee empowerment are crucial in driving project success in the fast-paced world of telecommunications. Like many other industries, the telecommunications sector faces significant challenges during project execution, including coordination issues, resource allocation, and time management [1]. These challenges often stem from poor leadership or insufficient employee empowerment, which can negatively impact project outcomes[2]. Leadership is especially critical in projects involving contractors and subcontractors, where misalignments can cause delays and inefficiencies. While transformational leadership (TL) has been widely recognized as a highly effective leadership style, its impact on project performance, especially in the context of Empowerment, is not yet fully understood [3, 4]. Transformational leadership has the potential to significantly improve employee engagement, motivation, and performance by focusing on vision, inspiration, and personal development [5]. However, the interplay between transformational leadership and employee empowerment remains under-explored. Employee empowerment, which gives individuals the authority and responsibility to make decisions and take ownership of their work, has been linked to enhanced productivity and job satisfaction [6]. When transformational leadership and employee empowerment come together, these two factors may create a powerful synergy that drives project success [7]. This study aims to explore the effects of transformational leadership on project performance, specifically by examining the moderating role of employee empowerment. By focusing on the telecom sector, this study will contribute to understanding how leadership styles and empowered teams can optimize project outcomes.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Transformational Leadership and Project Performance

Transformational leadership is widely regarded as motivating followers to exceed their expectations and work towards a collective vision, aligning personal goals with organizational objectives [8, 9]. TL is

known for its focus on inspiration, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration, all of which contribute to higher performance levels in various organizational contexts [10-12]. Studies indicate that transformational leaders can foster an environment that encourages creativity, teamwork, and innovation, essential for successful project delivery [13-15].

In project management, where the ability to lead teams towards a common goal is paramount, transformational leadership has shown a strong positive impact on project performance. For instance, Research by Han et al. (2020) found that transformational leaders significantly enhanced team motivation and commitment, resulting in higher project success rates [16]. These leaders create a vision that inspires teams and encourages high performance, essential for overcoming the challenges inherent in complex projects. As such, transformational leadership plays a vital role in driving project success by improving team collaboration, ensuring clear communication, and fostering an environment of continuous improvement [17].

2.2 Employee Empowerment

Employee empowerment gives employees more control over their work by providing autonomy, decision-making power, and the resources necessary to take initiative [18-20]. Empowered employees feel more involved in their work, which leads to higher job satisfaction, commitment, and performance [21, 22]. Empowerment is particularly relevant in project management, where employees, especially those at lower levels, need the autonomy to make decisions that affect project outcomes. This autonomy fosters a sense of ownership, accountability, and responsibility, all of which contribute to the project's overall performance [23-25].

Recent studies have highlighted the importance of employee empowerment in fostering innovation and improving work outcomes. For example, Yang and Choi (2009) found that empowered team employees showed significantly better performance in both productivity and innovation [26]. Furthermore, Empowerment has been shown to improve communication and collaboration within teams, making it a critical factor for successful project execution [27]. When empowered, employees are more likely to contribute meaningfully to the project, resulting in better decision-making, problem-solving, and project performance.

2.3 Moderating Role of Employee Empowerment

The role of employee empowerment as a moderator between transformational leadership and project performance has received limited attention. However, recent studies have suggested that empowered employees are more likely to respond positively to transformational leadership, enhancing its impact on performance [22, 28]. For example, Research by Kamoche (1992) and Nyambegera et al. (2000) indicated that empowering employees strengthens the relationship between leadership and organizational outcomes [29, 30]. In project management, empowered employees are better equipped to implement the vision and strategies laid out by transformational leaders, leading to better project outcomes.

Spreitzer and Quinn (1999) argued that combining transformational leadership and employee empowerment creates an environment where employees feel motivated, valued, and capable of achieving their goals [31]. This synergy can drive higher levels of performance, as employees are inspired by their leaders and empowered to take initiative and contribute to the project's success. As such, employee empowerment is not only an important factor but also plays a crucial role in enhancing the effectiveness of transformational leadership in driving project success.

2.4 Recent Research on Leadership, Empowerment, and Project Performance

Recent studies have reinforced the critical role of transformational leadership and employee empowerment in improving project performance. A survey by Hussein (2016) found that transformational leadership positively influenced organizational commitment, improving project outcomes [32]. Similarly, Tareeq (2016) highlighted that transformational leaders were more effective in motivating employees to achieve project goals, leading to improved performance [33]. These findings suggest that combining transformational leadership and employee empowerment creates a dynamic environment where leaders and employees are aligned towards achieving project success.

Furthermore, studies in the telecom sector have indicated that employee empowerment is crucial for enhancing project performance. Research by Usman et al. (2021) found that transformational leadership and employee empowerment significantly improved project performance in the telecom industry [34]. These findings emphasize the importance of creating an empowered workforce that can respond to the challenges and complexities of large-scale projects.

The literature highlights the significant positive relationship between transformational leadership, employee empowerment, and project performance. However, there is still a gap in understanding how employee empowerment moderates the impact of transformational leadership on project outcomes. While previous Research has examined these variables in isolation, few studies have explored their combined effect in the context of project management. This Research aims to fill this gap by investigating the role of employee empowerment in moderating the relationship between transformational leadership and project performance.

2.5 Problem Statement

The growing emphasis on leadership in organizational and project management contexts has highlighted the importance of effective leadership styles in achieving project success. However, the relationship between transformational leadership and project performance remains underexplored, particularly concerning the moderating role of employee empowerment. This Research investigates how transformational leadership impacts project performance and how employee empowerment may moderate this relationship. The problem lies in understanding the conditions under which transformational leadership is most effective and how Empowerment can enhance its impact on project outcomes.

2.6 Significance of the Study

This study is significant because it provides a deeper understanding of how leadership styles, particularly transformational leadership, affect project performance. By examining the role of employee empowerment, the study will offer valuable insights into how organizations can enhance project outcomes by adopting specific leadership strategies. The findings will benefit project managers, leaders, and organizations in the telecommunications industry, where leadership and Empowerment are critical to successful project delivery. This Research will also contribute to the academic literature by addressing a gap in understanding the interaction between leadership and Empowerment in project contexts. Moreover, the results will provide actionable recommendations for improving leadership practices and enhancing employee empowerment to drive better project performance.

2.7 Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for this study integrates several key theories related to leadership, Empowerment, and performance. Transformational Leadership Theory: This theory posits that leaders can inspire and motivate followers to exceed their self-interest for the organisation's good, resulting in higher performance [5, 35]. Employee Empowerment Theory indicates that Empowerment involves giving employees the autonomy and responsibility to make decisions and act independently, which has been shown to improve motivation and performance [6]. Social Exchange Theory suggests that the relationship

between leaders and followers is based on mutual benefit and reciprocity. Transformational leaders build trust and engagement, fostering a positive environment where Empowerment is more effective. Job Characteristics Theory highlights how job autonomy and Empowerment can improve employee motivation and performance by providing meaningful work and opportunities for personal growth [36]. By integrating these theories, the study explores how transformational leadership and employee empowerment influence project performance. Combining these two variables may create a work environment that maximizes employee potential and drives project success.

2.8 Research Questions

RQ1: How does transformational leadership influence project performance?

RQ2: Does employee empowerment moderate the relationship between transformational leadership and project performance?

3 Methodology

3.1 Research design

The research strategy employed for the study was a survey-based research design. Surveys are widely used in project management research due to their ability to efficiently collect large amounts of data from a diverse group of respondents. A questionnaire was distributed to employees across various positions (e.g., engineers, managers, supervisors, etc.) in telecom companies to assess the impact of transformational leadership and employee empowerment on project performance. The Research also incorporated case studies from telecom companies to contextualize the survey results. The Research followed the positivist philosophy, characterized by the use of structured questionnaires and quantitative data analysis. Positivism was suitable for the study because it allowed for testing hypotheses using observable, measurable data. The goal was to test the relationships between transformational leadership, employee empowerment, and project performance through empirical data collection and statistical analysis.

3.1.1 Population

The targeted population for the study included employees working in telecom companies, specifically engineers, managers, supervisors, and other supporting staff. These employees had diverse educational backgrounds and varying experience levels in their respective roles. The population also included male and female employees working across different organisational roles.

3.1.2 Sampling Technique

A stratified random sampling technique ensured that various employee designations (engineers, supervisors, managers, and other team members) were adequately represented. The population was divided into strata based on employee designations, and a random sample was selected from each stratum. This technique helped ensure that the survey results reflected employees' perspectives across different organisational roles and responsibilities.

3.1.3 Sample Size Calculation

Based on the total population of 940 employees, a sample size of 310 respondents was targeted. The sample size for each stratum (designation group) was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Sample Size for Stratum} = \left(\frac{\text{Size of Stratum}}{\text{Total Population}} \right) \times \text{Total Sample Size}$$

Table 1 illustrates the sample size calculation for each group:

Category	Size	Sample Size Formula	Sample Size
Engineers	143	$(310 / 940) * 143 = 47$	47
Supervisors	290	$(310 / 940) * 290 = 96$	96
Managers	129	$(310 / 940) * 129 = 43$	43
Other Team Members	378	$(310 / 940) * 378 = 125$	125
Total	940		310

3.2 Instruments

The primary instrument for data collection was a survey questionnaire. The questionnaire included items related to the three variables: transformational leadership, employee empowerment, and project performance. The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree, 5 = Strongly Agree) for each item.

3.2.1 Transformational Leadership Scale:

This scale was Developed by Hsing-Er Lin (2009). The transformational leadership scale assessed the extent to which leaders exhibited inspirational motivation, individualized consideration, and intellectual stimulation [37]. It included six items: "My leader articulates a clear vision for the future" and "My leader encourages me to think creatively." The Cronbach's alpha for this scale was reported as 0.87, indicating high internal consistency and reliability.

3.2.2 Employee Empowerment Scale:

This scale was Developed by Menon (1995). This scale evaluated the degree to which employees felt empowered in their roles, including autonomy, decision-making ability, and involvement in goal-setting [20]. It included 5 items, such as "I have the authority to make decisions in my job" and "I feel my manager values my opinions." The Cronbach's alpha for this scale was reported as 0.85, indicating a strong reliability level.

3.2.3 Project Performance Scale:

This scale was Developed by Kissi et al. (2013). The project performance scale evaluated the project's overall success, including factors like timeliness, cost management, and quality [8]. It included five items: "The project was completed on time" and "The project met the expected quality standards." The Cronbach's alpha for this scale was reported as 0.81, indicating satisfactory reliability.

3.3 Data Collection Procedures

Survey questionnaires were distributed to the selected sample from telecom companies, and participants were asked to complete the survey within a specified time frame. The questionnaires were collected and logged for analysis.

3.4 Data Analyses

Data were analysed using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) version 23. The internal consistency of the survey instrument was checked using Cronbach's alpha. A reliability coefficient of 0.7 or higher was considered acceptable. To ensure the validity of the scales, a KMO and Bartlett's test was performed to assess sampling adequacy, and factor analysis was conducted to identify underlying relationships among the survey items. Pearson's correlation was used to test the relationships between the study variables (transformational leadership, employee empowerment, and project performance). Multiple regression analyses assessed the direct and moderating effects of transformational leadership and employee empowerment on project performance. The outcomes of this regression analysis clarified the hypothetical effects of the study and determined whether significant associations and moderated effects existed.

4 Results

TABLE 1
Demographic characteristic of the sample (N=310)

Sr.no	Categories	Variables	f (%)
1	Qualification	Intermediate Graduate Postgraduate Ms/PhD	23 (7.4) 102 (32.9) 142 (45.8) 43 (13.9)
2	Gender	Male Female	246 (79.4) 64 (20.6)
3	Age	20-25 25-35 35-45 45 plus	32 (10.3) 56 (18.1) 123(39.7) 99 (31.9)
4	Experience	2-5 years 5-10 years 10-15 years 15 above	70 (22.6) 91 (29.4) 109 (35.2) 40 (12.9)

The survey sample consisted of 310 respondents representing various employee designations and demographics within telecom companies. Among the respondents, 47 (15%) were engineers, 95 (31%) were supervisors, 43 (14%) were managers, and 125 (40%) were from other roles, including assistants, supply chain employees, and operational staff. Respondents were grouped into four educational levels. 7% held an intermediate qualification (23 individuals), 32% were graduates (102 individuals), 46% had postgraduate qualifications (142 individuals), and 14% had MS/PhD degrees (43 individuals). This diverse mix of qualifications provides a broad perspective for the study. The sample was predominantly male, with 246 male respondents (79%) and 64 female respondents (21%). Although the female participation was lower, it still provided valuable insights into the study. Most respondents were aged between 35 and 45 years (39.7%) and 45 years and above (31.9%). The younger age groups (20-25 and 25-35 years) comprised 10.3% and 18.1% of the respondents, respectively, ensuring a mix of experience and perspectives across age groups. The highest response came from employees with 10-15 years of experience (35.2%), followed by those with 5-10 years (29.4%). The groups with 2-5 years and 15+ years of experience accounted for 22.6% and 12.9% of the responses, respectively.

TABLE 2
Summary of Reliability Test

S.no	Scale Name	No of Items	Cron Bach's Alpha
1	Transformational Leadership	6	.903
2	Employee empowerment	5	.884
3	Project Success	5	.812

The reliability test was conducted to evaluate the internal consistency of the scales used in this quantitative study. The study employed five scales: four independent and one dependent. The reliability results for each scale are presented in the table above. For the first scale, Transformational Leadership, which contains 6 items, the Cronbach’s Alpha value was found to be 0.903, indicating strong internal consistency, as it exceeds the acceptable threshold of 0.700. The second scale, Employee Empowerment, with 5 items, yielded a Cronbach’s Alpha of 0.884, demonstrating high reliability. The third scale, Project Success, which also consists of 5 items, returned a Cronbach’s Alpha of 0.812, further confirming its reliability. Overall, all scales demonstrated strong internal consistency, validating the reliability of the survey instrument for use in subsequent statistical analysis.

TABLE 3

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.674
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	719.245
	Df	3
	Sig.	.000

This test measures the sampling adequacy for respected survey, as the above table shows results against KMO & B test where the sampling adequacy has resulted as 67% which indicates that this survey has taken the justified sampling with adequate sample size and responses. Andy field book named (discovering statistics) in chapter of factor analysis Kaiser in 1974 suggested that the values higher than 0.5 are acceptable. Against all three variables in the survey, the significance level falls as excellent with value of 0.000. So this survey justifies the adequacy and validates the collected responses against processed instrument.

TABLE 4
Rotated Component Matrix

	Component		
	1	2	3
Q-1	.732		
Q-2		.903	
Q-3	.732		
Q-4	.766		
Q-5	.542	.466	
Q-6		.903	
Q-1	.765		
Q-2	.659		
Q-3	.731		
Q-4	.702		
Q-5		.903	
Q-1		.903	
Q-2			.642
Q-3			.827
Q-4			.836
Q-5			.803

Because all of the study variables for this survey have some degree of relationship among all the factors in survey, there are many ways that these subjected associations could be highlighted and represented. Andy's field book mentioned that the loading criterion is less than 0.4. This rotated component analysis has been processed with principal component matrix along with variomax technique which is representing

all patterns of association among survey factors. This rotation component analysis was processed for easier interpretation factors by distributing the component loadings against their associations.

Table 5
Analysis of correlation

		Transformational	Employee empowerment	Performance
Transformational	Pearson Correlation	1	*	
	Sig. (2-tailed)			
	N	310		
Employee empowerment	Pearson Correlation	.910**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	310	310	
Performance	Pearson Correlation	.629**	.663**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	310	310	310

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

This analysis examines the relationships between the research variables, as shown in the table above. It presents the Pearson correlation values and their significance levels (one-tailed or two-tailed) for the survey responses. The correlation between the independent variable, Transformational Leadership, and the dependent variable, Project Performance, was found to be 63%, with a two-tailed significance, indicating a meaningful relationship between these two variables. Similarly, the correlation between employee empowerment (the moderating variable) and project performance was 66%, showing a significant two-tailed relationship. The correlation between Transformational Leadership and Employee Empowerment was particularly strong at 91%, highlighting a significant relationship between these variables. Overall, the correlation analysis demonstrates significant relationships between all three variables, indicating that they are mutually related.

TABLE 6
Hierarchical regression for the prediction of employee empowerment

Models		R ²	β	F
Model 1		.39	.63**	201.39
(TL)				
Model 2		.44	.15**	26.38
(TL)+(EMT)			.53	
Model 3		.45	.34	1.72
(TL)+(EMT)			.66	
(TL)x(EMT)			-.32	
TotalR ²		.128		

Table 6 illustrates the moderating effect of Employee Empowerment on the relationship between Transformational Leadership and Project Performance. Three models were tested, with the first model showing that Transformational Leadership significantly predicted Employee Empowerment, explaining 39% of the variance in the dependent variable (R² = .39, p < .01, β = .63). The second model, which included both Transformational Leadership and Employee Empowerment, also proved significant (f(1,308) = 26.38, p < .01), with Employee Empowerment contributing 44% of the variance (R² = .44, p < .01, β = .15). In the third model, the interaction between Transformational Leadership and Employee Empowerment was tested for its impact on Project Performance. However, this model was found to be non-significant (f(1,307) = 1.72, p > .05), with both variables together explaining 45% of the variance (R² = .45, p = .35, β = .34).

Figure 1 Moderating effect of Employee empowerment in the relation between transformational leadership and project performance

In this graph, the red line shows the moderating impact of Employee empowerment, and the green line shows the relation between transformational leadership and project performance.

Transformational leadership and employee empowerment both variables have a high correlation, which shows that multi-co-linearity exists between both variables.

5 Discussion

This section discusses the study's findings, focusing on the relationships between transformational leadership, employee empowerment, project performance, and the moderating role of employee empowerment. The results indicate a strong correlation between the variables, with implications for leadership practices in the telecommunications industry.

The results from the Pearson correlation analysis showed a significant positive relationship between transformational leadership and project performance. These findings are consistent with recent Research, which suggests that transformational leadership positively influences organizational and project outcomes. For instance, a study by Nielsen et al. (2018) emphasized the importance of transformational leadership in improving team effectiveness and project performance, noting that transformational leaders inspire and motivate employees to achieve higher levels of performance by aligning their personal goals with organizational objectives [38]. This aligns with Riggio, and Newstead, (2023), who found that transformational leadership enhances team cohesion, problem-solving, and overall performance by fostering a positive work environment and a shared vision [39].

In a study by García-Morales et al. (2020), transformational leadership was also found to be crucial for driving performance in innovation-driven projects, particularly in industries requiring constant adaptation and change, such as telecommunications [40]. The current study corroborates these findings, suggesting that transformational leaders can lead their teams to better project outcomes by demonstrating inspirational motivation and intellectual stimulation. Transformational leaders' ability to engage with employees and align them with organizational goals results in improved performance, as they foster an environment that encourages innovation and problem-solving [41].

The analysis revealed a strong positive correlation between employee empowerment and project performance, indicating that empowering employees significantly enhances their performance and, in turn, the project's overall success. This finding is in line with recent studies by Kim et al. (2020), who found that employee empowerment increases employees' autonomy and decision-making abilities, leading to improved job satisfaction and higher performance [42]. Furthermore, a study by Khan et al. (2020)

highlighted that empowered employees tend to take more ownership of their roles, which results in better project outcomes and increased organizational performance [43].

Research by Laschinger et al. (2016) supports these findings by suggesting that employee empowerment fosters a sense of autonomy and control, enhancing employee motivation and engagement, ultimately leading to higher performance [44]. Similarly, a study by Choi and Kim (2019) found that empowered employees exhibited greater organizational commitment and were more likely to contribute to the successful delivery of projects. The results of this study reinforce the importance of empowering employees as a strategy for enhancing performance, particularly in industries like telecommunications where team collaboration and innovation are essential for success [45].

The regression analysis showed an insignificant moderating effect of employee empowerment in the relationship between transformational leadership and project performance. This result is inconsistent with previous Research that suggested employee empowerment could act as a moderator in leadership-performance relationships. For example, a study by Mehmood et al. (2019) found that employee empowerment strengthens the relationship between transformational leadership and employee performance by providing employees with the tools and autonomy to act on their leader's vision [46]. However, the current study suggests that the moderating effect of employee empowerment may not be as pronounced in the context of telecom projects, where the work environment may not provide sufficient autonomy or decision-making authority for Empowerment to have a significant impact.

This could be explained by the findings of a study by Salas-Vallina et al. (2020), which argued that while transformational leadership and employee empowerment are both important, their combined effects on performance depend heavily on contextual factors, such as the organizational culture and the nature of the projects [47]. Telecom projects, which often have rigid structures and time-sensitive goals, may limit the potential of employee empowerment to moderate the relationship between transformational leadership and project performance. This suggests that organizational context plays a crucial role in determining how leadership behaviours and empowerment initiatives affect project outcomes.

The results also indicated a high correlation between transformational leadership and employee empowerment, suggesting potential multicollinearity between these two variables. Multicollinearity occurs when independent variables are highly correlated, which can distort the results of regression analysis [48]. This study's high correlation between transformational leadership and employee empowerment may have contributed to the insignificant moderating effect observed. When these two variables are strongly correlated, isolating their individual effects on project performance becomes difficult.

This finding is consistent with the work of Audenaert et al. (2020), who argued that transformational leadership and employee empowerment are often intertwined, as transformational leaders tend to empower their followers as part of their leadership approach [49]. However, the challenge of multicollinearity may limit the ability to draw clear conclusions about the moderating role of Empowerment, suggesting that future Research should consider additional factors or use techniques such as structural equation modelling to better assess the unique contributions of each variable.

5.1 Conclusion

In conclusion, the study provides valuable insights into the relationships between transformational leadership, employee empowerment, and project performance. While transformational leadership and employee empowerment were found to be positively correlated with project performance, the moderating effect of employee empowerment was not significant. These findings underscore the importance of transformational leadership in driving project success and highlight the need for organizations to empower their employees to foster a high-performance culture. Future Research should explore additional variables that may influence the relationship between these factors and examine the role of multicollinearity in leadership-performance studies.

5.2 Limitations and suggestions

This study has several limitations, including the absence of financial measures related to employee empowerment and leadership style, the focus on the telecommunications sector, and the cross-sectional research design, which limits its ability to capture dynamic changes over time. Additionally, contextual factors such as organizational culture and external economic conditions were not considered, which could influence the results. Future Research could address these limitations by incorporating financial incentives to assess their combined impact with empowerment strategies, expanding the scope to include multiple industries, adopting a longitudinal design to track the effects over time, and exploring additional contextual variables. Furthermore, investigating other moderating and mediating factors, such as organizational support and job autonomy, and comparing transformational leadership with other leadership styles, could provide a more comprehensive understanding of how these elements affect project performance in various settings.

5.3 Implications for Practice

The findings of this study highlight the importance of transformational leadership and employee empowerment for enhancing project performance in the telecommunications industry. Organizations should focus on developing transformational leadership qualities in their managers, such as fostering a clear vision, encouraging creativity, and offering individualized support. These leadership behaviours are essential for motivating employees and improving overall project outcomes. Furthermore, while employee empowerment was found to impact project performance directly, the moderating role of Empowerment was not as significant as expected. This suggests that while Empowerment is important, its effectiveness in amplifying the influence of transformational leadership may depend on other factors, such as organizational culture, job autonomy, and the nature of the work itself. Organizations should carefully assess the level of autonomy and decision-making power granted to employees, ensuring that empowerment initiatives align with the project's strategic objectives.

References

- [1] K. Thompson, *Leadership best practices and employee performance: A phenomenological telecommunications industry study*. University of Phoenix, 2015.
- [2] T. P. L. Nguyen, T. T. Nguyen, C. D. Duong, and X. H. Doan, "The effects of transformational leadership on employee creativity in Vietnam telecommunications enterprises," *Management Decision*, vol. 60, no. 3, pp. 837-857, 2022.
- [3] A. F. Soliman, "The effect of leadership empowerment on technology transfer effectiveness: A proposed model: An applied study on the telecommunication companies in one of the developing countries," *The Journal of High Technology Management Research*, vol. 31, no. 1, p. 100371, 2020.
- [4] R. Al Saed and M. Al Saed, "The impact of transformational leadership on enhancing organizational trust: Moderating role of empowerment," *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, vol. 21, no. 4, p. 101, 2023.
- [5] B. M. Bass and R. E. Riggio, *Transformational leadership*. Psychology press, 2006.
- [6] G. M. Spreitzer, "Psychological empowerment in the workplace: Dimensions, measurement, and validation," *Academy of management Journal*, vol. 38, no. 5, pp. 1442-1465, 1995.
- [7] H. Santoso, E. Elidjen, S. Abdinagoro, and M. Arief, "The role of creative self-efficacy, transformational leadership, and digital literacy in supporting performance through innovative work behavior: Evidence from telecommunications industry," *Management Science Letters*, vol. 9, no. 13, pp. 2305-2314, 2019.
- [8] J. Kissi, A. Dainty, and M. Tuuli, "Examining the role of transformational leadership of portfolio managers in project performance," *International Journal of project management*, vol. 31, no. 4, pp. 485-497, 2013.

- [9] N. Zhao, D. Fan, and Y. Chen, "Understanding the Impact of Transformational Leadership on Project Success: A Meta - Analysis Perspective," *Computational Intelligence and Neuroscience*, vol. 2021, no. 1, p. 7517791, 2021.
- [10] D. A. Aga, N. Noorderhaven, and B. Vallejo, "Transformational leadership and project success: The mediating role of team-building," *International journal of project management*, vol. 34, no. 5, pp. 806-818, 2016.
- [11] M. Z. Fareed and Q. Su, "Transformational leadership and project success: A mediating role of public service motivation," *Administration & Society*, vol. 54, no. 4, pp. 690-713, 2022.
- [12] F. J. Yammarino, M. Cheong, J. Kim, and C.-Y. Tsai, "Is leadership more than "I like my boss"?", in *Research in personnel and human resources management*, vol. 38: Emerald Publishing Limited, 2020, pp. 1-55.
- [13] A. Klaić, M. J. Burtscher, and K. Jonas, "Fostering team innovation and learning by means of team - centric transformational leadership: The role of teamwork quality," *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, vol. 93, no. 4, pp. 942-966, 2020.
- [14] S. Rais and B. Rubini, "Increasing Teacher Creativity through Strengthening Transformational Leadership, Teamwork, and Work Engagement," *Pegem Journal of Education and Instruction*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 232-241, 2022.
- [15] G. Bosselut, L. Guilbert, and L. Chareyre, "Transformational leadership and creativity in sport: Examining the mediating role of support for innovation," *Journal of Sports Sciences*, vol. 38, no. 23, pp. 2698-2707, 2020.
- [16] S.-H. Han, E. G. Oh, and S. P. Kang, "The link between transformational leadership and work-related performance: moderated-mediating roles of meaningfulness and job characteristics," *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, vol. 41, no. 4, pp. 519-533, 2020.
- [17] S. M. J. Iqbal, U. Zaman, S. H. Siddiqui, and M. K. Imran, "Influence of transformational leadership factors on project success," *Pakistan Journal of Commerce and Social Sciences (PJCSS)*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 231-256, 2019.
- [18] K. Okochi and B. W. Ateke, "Employee empowerment: A strategy for optimizing employee performance," *Nigerian Journal of Business and Social Review*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 125-137, 2020.
- [19] H. M. Vu, "Employee empowerment and empowering leadership: A literature review," 2020.
- [20] S. T. Menon, "Employee empowerment: Definition, measurement and construct validation," 1995.
- [21] A. Abou Elnaga and A. Imran, "The impact of employee empowerment on job satisfaction theoretical study," *American Journal of Research Communication*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 13-26, 2014.
- [22] S. L. Choi, C. F. Goh, M. B. H. Adam, and O. K. Tan, "Transformational leadership, empowerment, and job satisfaction: the mediating role of employee empowerment," *Human resources for health*, vol. 14, pp. 1-14, 2016.
- [23] R. Matei and C. Veith, "Empowerment and Engagement: The Role of Autonomy and Feedback in Fostering Employee Motivation," *Manager (University of Bucharest, Faculty of Business & Administration)*, vol. 37, no. 1, 2023.
- [24] J. Alshemmari, "An empirical study on employee empowerment role in increasing efficiency of employee performance," *Journal of Logistics, Informatics and Service Science*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 52-71, 2023.
- [25] C. L. Krog and K. Govender, "The relationship between servant leadership and employee empowerment, commitment, trust and innovative behaviour: A project management perspective," *SA Journal of Human Resource Management*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 1-12, 2015.
- [26] S. B. Yang and S. Ok Choi, "Employee empowerment and team performance: Autonomy, responsibility, information, and creativity," *Team Performance Management: An International Journal*, vol. 15, no. 5/6, pp. 289-301, 2009.

- [27] M. P. Idua, "The influence of institutional factors and job related attitudes on the relationship between employee empowerment and performance of public universities in Kenya," University of Nairobi, 2014.
- [28] C. Magasi, "The role of transformational leadership on employee performance: A perspective of employee empowerment," *European Journal of Business and Management Research*, vol. 6, no. 6, pp. 21-28, 2021.
- [29] K. Kamoche, "Toward a model of HRM in Africa," 1992.
- [30] S. M. Nyambegera, P. Sparrow, and K. Daniels, "The impact of cultural value orientations on individual HRM preferences in developing countries: lessons from Kenyan organizations," *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 639-663, 2000.
- [31] G. M. Spreitzer, S. C. De Janasz, and R. E. Quinn, "Empowered to lead: The role of psychological empowerment in leadership," *Journal of Organizational Behavior: The International Journal of Industrial, Occupational and Organizational Psychology and Behavior*, vol. 20, no. 4, pp. 511-526, 1999.
- [32] R. Al-Hussein, "The relation between psychological empowerment and job satisfaction among nurses," *Medico Legal. Update*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 1353-1359, 2020.
- [33] T. Tawfik *et al.*, "The economic empowerment of saudi women in the light of saudi vision 2030," *Asian Econ. Financ. Rev.*, vol. 10, pp. 1269-1279, 2020.
- [34] M. Usman, M. Ali, C. Ogbonnaya, and M. T. Babalola, "Fueling the intrapreneurial spirit: A closer look at how spiritual leadership motivates employee intrapreneurial behaviors," *Tourism Management*, vol. 83, p. 104227, 2021.
- [35] B. M. Bass and M. Bass Bernard, "Leadership and performance beyond expectations," 1985.
- [36] J. R. Hackman and G. R. Oldham, "Motivation through the design of work: Test of a theory," *Organizational behavior and human performance*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 250-279, 1976.
- [37] H.-E. Lin, *The impact of senior leadership and organizational culture on innovation in Taiwanese companies*. Maastricht School of Management, 2009.
- [38] L. Nielsen *et al.*, "The NIH Science of Behavior Change Program: Transforming the science through a focus on mechanisms of change," *Behaviour research and therapy*, vol. 101, pp. 3-11, 2018.
- [39] R. E. Riggio and T. Newstead, "Crisis leadership," *Annual Review of Organizational Psychology and Organizational Behavior*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 201-224, 2023.
- [40] V. J. García-Morales, R. Martín-Rojas, and R. Garde-Sánchez, "How to encourage social entrepreneurship action? Using web 2.0 technologies in higher education institutions," *Journal of Business Ethics*, vol. 161, pp. 329-350, 2020.
- [41] S. Hassan, G. Prussia, R. Mahsud, and G. Yukl, "How leader networking, external monitoring, and representing are relevant for effective leadership," *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, vol. 39, no. 4, pp. 454-467, 2018.
- [42] E.-J. Kim and S. Park, "Transformational leadership, knowledge sharing, organizational climate and learning: an empirical study," *Leadership & organization development journal*, vol. 41, no. 6, pp. 761-775, 2020.
- [43] H. Khan, M. Rehmat, T. H. Butt, S. Farooqi, and J. Asim, "Impact of transformational leadership on work performance, burnout and social loafing: a mediation model," *Future Business Journal*, vol. 6, no. 1, p. 40, 2020.
- [44] H. K. Laschinger, E. Read, and J. Zhu, "23. Employee empowerment and organizational commitment," *Handbook of employee commitment*, vol. 319, 2016.
- [45] S. Choi and M. Kim, "Effects of structural empowerment and professional governance on autonomy and job satisfaction of the Korean nurses," *Journal of nursing management*, vol. 27, no. 8, pp. 1664-1672, 2019.

- [46] M. S. Mehmood, Z. Jian, A. Waheed, A. Younas, and S. Z. Khan, "Impact of entrepreneurial leadership on employee's innovative behavior: mediating role of psychological empowerment," in *Proceedings of the 2019 3rd International Conference on Management Engineering, Software Engineering and Service Sciences*, 2019, pp. 223-229.
- [47] A. Salas-Vallina, C. Simone, and R. Fernández-Guerrero, "The human side of leadership: Inspirational leadership effects on follower characteristics and happiness at work (HAW)," *Journal of Business Research*, vol. 107, pp. 162-171, 2020.
- [48] S. L. Martin, H. Liao, and E. M. Campbell, "Directive versus empowering leadership: A field experiment comparing impacts on task proficiency and proactivity," *Academy of management Journal*, vol. 56, no. 5, pp. 1372-1395, 2013.
- [49] M. Audenaert, A. Decramer, and B. George, "How to foster employee quality of life: The role of employee performance management and authentic leadership," *Evaluation and Program Planning*, vol. 85, p. 101909, 2021.